

Feynman-Lagrangian Approach to Density Matrix/Partition Function for High Temperature

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It is known one may use Feynman's path integral approach to solve for a quantum propagator. Setting $it=b$ where $b=1/T_p$ (T_p =temperature), the approach may also be used to calculate the partition function (which is linked to a density matrix calculation). Furthermore, one may assume a form for the propagator and note that it is a solution of the time-dependent Schrodinger equation with $i d/dt$ replaced with $-d/db$. For example, setting $P= Q(t) \exp[i (b(t)XX + g(t)YY + g1(t) XY)]$ and equating coefficients for XX , XY and YY separately (and equating imaginary terms for $Q(t)$), yields differential equations for $Q(t)$, $b(t)$, $g(t)$ and $g1(t)$.

In (1), this approach is used to find the partition function for an oscillator potential with an extra ax term. The differential equations are established and solved, then the solutions are expanded in powers of $b=1/T_p$ i.e. for high temperature (tiny b) and a high-temperature partition function obtained.

In (2), we calculated the propagator (and hence partition function) using $Q(t) \exp(i \text{Action})$ where $\text{Action} = \int dt (0,T) L$ where L is the Lagrangian. In this approach: $x(t)= XA(T-t)/A(T) + Y A(t-0)/A(T)$ (3) where X and Y are parameters, $T=T_f$ and $T_i=0$ and T is associated with $b=1/T_p$. We argue in this note, that one may perform a first order expansion in $b=1/T_p$ of $A(T-t)$ and $A(t-0)$ and then perform the integral $\int dt L$. This yields the high temperature result for the oscillator plus ax potential partition function without any need of solving differential equations and then taking high temperature limits.

Differential Equation Approach of (1)

In (1), the following Hamiltonian is considered:

$$H= -1/2m d/dx d/dx + .5m \omega^2 x^2 + \sqrt{m\omega} w/2 a (x - d/\sqrt{m\omega}) \quad ((1))$$

A variable change is made: $e1= \sqrt{m\omega} x$ and $b=1/\text{Temperature} = 1/T_p = 2f/\omega$ ((2))

The following form is assumed for the partition function (i.e. propagator with $it=b$):

$$P = \text{Exp}\{ -[a(f) e1^*e1 + b1(f)e1 + c1(f)] \} \quad ((3))$$

P is inserted into the time dependent Schrodinger equation with $i d/dt$ replaced with $-d/db$. Coefficients of $e1^*e1$, $e1$ etc are equated independently to lead to a set of differential equations. We only list the equation for $a(f)$ here (the rest are given in (1)).

$$da/df = 1- 4 a^2 \quad ((4)) \quad (\text{This equation also appears in (2).})$$

Solving for $a(f)$ yields $\coth(2f)$ ((5))

Taking the high temperature, low f limit of ((5)) yields $1/2f$ ((6))

Ultimately, the high temperature limit of P is found to be:

$$P = \sqrt{m\omega/4\pi^2 f} \exp\{- (e_1 - e_1')(e_1 - e_1')/4f\} \quad ((7))$$

Thus, ((7)) is the result for the high temperature case partition function.

Lagrangian Approach to the Partition Function

In (2), we calculated the Feynman propagator using $Q(t) \exp(i \text{Action})$ where $\text{Action} = \int_{0,T} dt L$, L being the Lagrangian. Following (3):

$$x(t) = X A(T-t)/A(T) + Y A(t-0)/A(T) \text{ where } A(t) \text{ is a solution of Newton's second law} \quad ((8))$$

$T=T_f$ and $T_i=0$. From ((8)), one may see that $A(0)=0$. Note T is associated with $1/T_p$ where T_p is temperature because one uses it $= b=1/T_p$ when linking the propagator to the partition function.

We found in (2), that for a propagator of the form: $Q(t) \exp\{i (b_1(t)XX + g(t)YY + g_1(t)XY)\}$,

$$b_1(t) = .5m \, dA/dt / A(T) \quad ((9))$$

This result was obtained by using ((8)) to calculate $\int dt$ Lagrangian.

Here, we propose using this approach for the partition function and already taking the high temperature limit of $A(t)$ before integrating that Lagrangian. This should lead to the high energy limit for the partition function (propagator with $it=b$).

First, we set $m=w=1$ to simplify the problem. Then, for the XX coefficient:

$$1/[A(T)A(T)] \{ \int_{0,T} dt .5 \, dA/dt \, dA/dt + .5 A(T-t)A(T-t) \} \quad ((10))$$

One may note that the extra potential term x -constant does not affect the XX coefficient in the partition function.

$A(t)$ is a solution of $m \, d/dt \, dA/dt = -k A$, but use is not made of this equation when calculating to first order. The equation, however, could be used if one wished to calculate to higher orders. Rather, $A(T-t)$ is expanded in a $T-t$ series i.e.

$$A(T-t) = a_1(T-t) + \dots \quad \text{Note: } A(0)=0 \text{ from ((8)) so the first term is } a_1(T-t) \text{ and not a constant.}$$

In such a case, only the dA/dt term yields a leading term in ((10)) where T is associated with $b=1/T_p$.

$$1/[A(T)A(T)] \approx 1/(2T) = .5/T_p \quad ((11))$$

((11)) is identical to the low f limit of $a(f) = .5 \coth(2f) = 1/(4f) = T_p/(2)$ where $f = .5/T_p$ for $m=w=1$.

Thus, there is no need to solve a differential equation and then take a low f limit of the solution when one may already take a low T (i.e. low b or low f) limit of the solution to Newton's second law (even ignoring Newton's second law to first order) and evaluate: $\int_0^T dt L$ where L is the Lagrangian to obtain the same low b (high T_p =temperature) result.

Conclusion

In conclusion, in (1) the partition function (propagator) is solved by postulating a form which is substituted into the time-dependent Schrodinger equation with id/dt replaced with $-d/db$ where $b=1/T_p$, T_p being temperature. This leads to a set of differential equations in $b=1/T_p$ which may be solved. Finally, the high temperature (T_p) limit is taken.

In this note, we propose an alternative approach. We suggest using $Q(t)\exp(i \text{Action})$ to calculate the propagator (partition function) with $x(t) = XA(T-t)/A(T-t) + Y A(t)/A(T)$ and expanding $A(T-t)$ as a power series of $T-t$ noting that $A(T)=0$ i.e. $A(T-t) = a_1(T-t)$. One may then perform the Lagrangian integral in this low T or high T_p (Temperature) limit and obtain the result of (1) without solving a differential equation and taking the high temperature limit.

References

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